

Proposed Marketing Strategy for Initiation Development and Increase Sales Performance of CV Jonifer Embroidery

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ABSTRACT: Textile activities continue to expand their role along with the times and technology, not only for the purposes of art-culture and clothing needs in a limited environment, but this activity already be used as a source of income. One of the businesses engaged in the field of Textiles and Textile Products is Jonifer Embroidery Convection. This company is one of the pioneers in the convection business in Padang and has been operating for 12 years. The problem the company is currently experiencing is a decline in sales from 2021 to 2022. Therefore, this research will focus on finding the main problems related to Jonifer Embroidery's internal and external conditions to create a marketing strategy using the SWOT Matrix which is then formulated through the TOWS Matrix and produce a new marketing strategy for the Jonifer Embroidery. The proposed marketing strategy consists of cooperating with companies or communities, providing product guarantees to maintain customer trust, optimizing business websites for promotional media, product innovation, marketing using social media, creating customer loyalty programs, making attractive banners, offering several promotions sales, and selecting Key Opinion Leaders (KOL).

KEYWORDS: External Analysis, Internal Analysis, Marketing Strategy, SWOT, TOWS

INTRODUCTION

Based on industrial analysis data showing that the Textile and Apparel Industry as a labor-intensive industry contributes to the number of workers reaching 2.67% and became the second largest industry in the processing industry category. In addition, in 2022, the contribution of this industry's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) will reach 6.56% of the non-oil and gas processing industry [1]. Therefore, the Textile and Apparel Industry is one of the main contributing industries in the manufacturing sector and one of the five largest industries in the non-oil and gas processing industry category. The growth of the textile and apparel industry in Indonesia increased sharply by 13.10% in 2022 [2]. This positive trend will also have an impact on derivative industries from the textile and apparel industry throughout Indonesia, including in the city of Padang. Based on data BPS 2022, The Textile and Apparel Industry is in the fourth largest position in Padang[1]. This is due to the large number of enthusiasts and market demand regarding textile and apparel products. Based on these conditions, it requires business actors in the convection sector to innovate in order to maintain their company. Based on the company's sales data, there has been a decline in sales from the first quarter of 2021 to 2022. Considering this condition, Jonifer Embroidery needs to adjust a suitable new marketing strategy to manage their marketing effort based on its current condition to gain better sales performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer buying behavior is how people and households buy goods and services for their own use. Consumers all over the world are very different in terms of their age, income, level of education, and tastes[3]. Also, they buy a huge range of goods and services. How these different customers feel about each other and the rest of the world affects what products, services, and companies they choose. Consumer behavior is what people do when they look for, buy, use, evaluate, and decide to stop using products, services, and ideas. Marketing strategy is the marketing plan that companies use to try to give customers what they want and build profitable relationships with them[4]. Marketing strategy is a set of goals, objectives, policies, and rules that tell the company's marketing efforts at each level what to do and how to do it. This is especially important because the company's competitive environment and conditions are always changing. So, the marketing strategy must be based on an analysis of the company's internal and external environments. This includes an analysis of the company's strengths and weaknesses, as well as an analysis of the opportunities and threats it faces from the outside world[5].

A thorough analysis of the company's internal and external environments was used to come up with the marketing strategy. The outside world of the company is always changing quickly, which creates both opportunities and threats from the company's main

competitors and the always-changing business climate. Changes in external factors have effects on internal factors as well, like how the company's strengths and weaknesses change. Based on what has been said so far, the marketing strategy is a comprehensive and well-thought-out plan for marketing. It includes details about the series of marketing activities that the company must do. The company's management will be able to make decisions about strategic marketing activities once these analyses are done.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, methods that are both qualitative and descriptive are used. Qualitative research methods collect interpretations to learn more about how a business works. There are two kinds of data used in this study: first-hand data and data that has already been collected. The executives who took part in the in-depth interviews that gave this study its main data were the CEO and the General Managers. A questionnaire survey of the company's potential clients was another way to get first-hand information. Secondary data for this study came from internal company reports, publications, magazines, newspaper articles, and other types of media. All of the data will be put through a SWOT analysis to find out the company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Any results of the analysis of the framework will be. A SWOT analysis will be done on all of the data to find out what the company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Any results from the analysis of the framework will be put together. The 4P marketing mix and the digital marketing marketing strategy will be used to decide on the strategy.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. SWOT

Strengths include the company's own skills, resources, and good circumstances that may help it serve its customers and reach its goals. Weaknesses include things like the company's own limitations and outside problems that could hurt its performance. Opportunities are good things or trends in the outside world that a company might be able to use to its benefit. Threats are negative external factors or trends that could make it hard to do well. The results of JE's internal and external analysis evaluations are shown in the table below.

Strength	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Affordable price Sufficient clothing production technology Good networking of owners Strategic location in the downtown area 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less product variety and materials Lack of social media as a promotional activity Limited product design Lack of sales promotion
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government comprehensive support such as the development of the TPT industry through Industry 4.0 Increasing Gross Domestic (GDP) Product related to the textile and apparel industry Increasing Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) in Padang The potential population in the local market especially in Padang city Growing penetration of internet Low bargaining power of suppliers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low barriers of new entrant, considering the easiness starting this business A large number and high intensity of competitors High Power of Buyers Existing competitors had strong awareness (attractive banners)

B. TOWS ANALYSIS

Adjusting for key internal and external factors is the hardest part of making a SWOT matrix, and it takes a lot of thought. This matrix is an important matching tool that helps managers come up with four types of strategies: SO Strategies, WO Strategies, ST Strategies, and WT Strategies. This method could be used to come up with the strategies and specific actions needed to put those strategies into action. After figuring out the situational analysis, which was summed up by SWOT, the results of the TOWS Matrix for JE convection are shown below.

TOWS Matrix	Strengths (S)	Weaknesses (W)
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Affordable price Sufficient clothing production technology Good networking of owners Strategic location in the downtown area 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Less product variety and materials Lack of social media as a promotional activity Limited product design Lack of sales promotion
Opportunities (O)	SO Strategies	WO Strategies
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Government comprehensive support such as the development of the TPT industry through Industry 4.0 Increasing Gross Domestic (GDP) Product related to the textile and apparel industry Increasing Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) in Padang The potential population in the local market especially in Padang city Growing penetration of internet and social media Low bargaining power of suppliers 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Establish cooperation with companies or community (S1-S4, O1-O4) Providing guarantees product to maintain customer trust (S2, S3,O2-O4) Optimizing business website for media promoting (S1,S2, O2-O5) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Product innovations in terms of design, material and sizing (W1,W3,O1,O4,O6) Proposed social media activity (W2,O2, O3,O4,O5)
Threats (T)	ST Strategies	WT Strategies
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Low barriers of new entrant, considering the easiness starting this business A large number and high intensity of competitors High Power of Buyers Existing competitors had strong awareness (attractive banners) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Create customer loyalty program (S1-S3, T1-T3) Create an attractive banner in front of the store that has a strategic location to convince customer (S1, S4, T1-T4) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Frequently offer several sales promotion (W4, T1-T3) Choose the right key Opinion Leader (KOL) (W2, T1-T3)

C. MARKETING STRATEGY FOR JONIFER EMBROIDERY

1. Product

• **Product innovations in terms of design, material, and sizing**

Jonifer embroidery is still weak competitive because of a few innovations of design, material, and sizes. This can be seen based on the results of a competitor analysis survey, where JE convection offers fewer products and materials than competitors in the same industry. JE convection can add other types of materials such as American drill union, American drill gorilla, Japan drill, Japan drill kings, toyobo, American drill ventura, ripstop us army, dryfit jarum, taslan, cotton combed, lacoste cvc, combed premium 30 s, UV Milano, American drill Alonso, fleece cotton, carded 30 s, gloria, putra mill, jersey, taipan tropical, Texas drill, Fernando Alonso dril, combed lakatex and cotton bamboo. In terms of product innovation, it is important for JE convection to develop new products to increase the variety of its products and serve new target markets

2. Promotion

• **Establish cooperation with companies or community**

Based on interviews conducted with the owner Jonifer Convection, he said that JE Convection was not very active in collaborating with outsiders. The JE convection team should be more active in collaborating with other communities or companies. One of the actions that Jonifer Embroidery can take is to be more aggressive in building cooperation.

• **Providing guarantees product to maintain customer trust**

The purpose of providing a guarantee for every product order at JE convection is to maintain customer trust. However, this product guarantees that the customer can use it if there is an error from convection in producing the product. This product warranty can be used with the following criteria; if there are errors in design, errors in size, improper sewing, and other defective product categories.

• **Proposed Social Media Marketing**

JE convection must provide something different and interesting for the content on their social media. There are several things that can be done to create interesting content for JE convection's social media, one of which is making daily vlog on social media about the process production from design, process, and packaging. Interesting content will affect JE's brand awareness. Besides that, it will also attract more potential customers who are interested in ordering JE's product. JE convection can expand its social media platform, which currently include Instagram, Facebook and Tik-Tok to reach more target market in today's technology-filled era

• **Optimizing business website for media promoting**

A product's official website can encourage people to buy it. Websites give a business a more professional look and can help customers trust the brand more. JE convection already has a website, but in an interview, the owner said that the official Jonifer Embroidery website is not updated. The website also doesn't have enough information about the products and materials it sells. Because of this, Jonifer Embroidery needs to make the most of its website as a way to promote the business.

• **Create customer loyalty program**

Jonifer Embroidery has to deal with a lot of competition in the convection business industry, which is one of the problems it faces. Customers find it easier to switch to competitors as the convection industry grows, so customer loyalty tends to be low and unstable. So, JE convection needs to have a customer loyalty program to keep track of their relationships with customers and encourage them to buy from them again. Loyalty programs are meant to keep customers coming back by giving them benefits over time (Dowling and Uncles). Customers and businesses can both benefit from loyalty programs. As an incentive, a company can offer rewards to customers who buy from them often by giving them benefits based on how much they have bought over time.

• **Frequently offer several sales promotion**

One example of a sales promotion offered by the JE convection is a discount of Rp. 2000/pcs with many orders, but it is not explained in detail how much the minimum purchase is to get a discount. Therefore, JE should be more detailed in implementing discount that will be given to consumers, for example, a 10% disc for a minimum purchase of 50 pcs or a 10% disc for the end of the month with the number of orders in accordance with the terms and conditions.

- **Choose the right key Opinion Leader (KOL) to increase engagements and convert leads to sales**
Key opinion leaders had a big impact to increase the engagement of the fashion industry. JE convection should choose the right Key Opinion Leader or Instagram called it “influencer”. The first step in determining an influencer is that the influencer's characteristics must match the product to be offered. The next step is Jonifer Embroidery should be analyzed one by one by comparing the likes, comments, followers, and their engagement. Since the target market of Jonifer Embroidery is people who live in Padang and the products offered are mostly uniforms or work clothes, then JE convection is currently selecting influencers that fit that category.
- **Create an attractive banner in front of the store that has a strategic location to convince customer**
Based on the marketing mix analysis in the previous chapter, it is known that Jonifer Embroidery's location is Dr. Sutomo No.2, Simpang Haru, Padang, West Sumatra is a strategic location because this location is close to residential areas, offices, and Andalas University (one of the biggest universities in Padang). With this strategic location, JE convection can position a banner in front of the shop, where the banner must be attractive and convincing, and the banner must also contain brief information regarding the products offered so that if anyone passing through the shop can be aware of the existence of Jonifer Embroidery.

CONCLUSION

The plan for putting Jonifer Embroidery Convection into action is changed based on which of the following activities must be done first. Each strategic recommendation is broken down into detailed activity and process stages that can be used as a guide to make it easier to carry out. In this study, the implementation plan is mostly about the product and how to promote it. Based on past research, it was found that the product has a big impact on how people see the quality of the product, and that promotion has a big impact on how well people know the brand. For this reason, companies must develop product marketing strategies and strategies to increase consumer purchasing intentions. For products, the strategy used is product innovation which consists of adding product types, designs, materials, and sizes. Based on competitor analysis, Jonifer Embroidery has fewer product lines compared to the other three competitors. In addition, the designs from JE convection also do not have a design catalog. Therefore, the author proposes to create a catalog for product designs in the form of a portfolio. According to SWOT analysis, it was found that the biggest problem with Jonifer Embroidery was related to its promotion. Therefore, based on the previous TOWS analysis, the marketing strategy for this convection is dominated by promotions. This is in accordance with the interviews that the authors conducted with CEOs and General Managers who said that the lack of promotion caused sales to decline. The proposed promotion strategy consists of establishing partnerships, making guarantees, optimizing websites, creating social media accounts such as Instagram and Tik-Tok, making loyalty cards, making attractive banners, making sales promotions such as product discounts and collaborating with influencers. Since there are no employees in the marketing field, Jonifer Embroidery needs to recruit employees so that these promotional activities can run effectively and efficiently

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